

The Features of Organizing a Master Preparation in Kazakhstan

A. Bulatbayeva, A. Kusainov

II. CONTENT OF MASTER PREPARATION

Abstract—In this article has been analyzed Kazakhstani experience in organizing the system after the institute of higher education, legislative-regulative assurance of master preparation, and statistic data in the republic. Have been the features of projecting the master programs, a condition of realization of studying credit system, have been analyzed the technologies of research teaching masters. In conclusion have been given some recommendation on creating personal-oriented environment of research teaching masters.

Keywords—Personal-oriented Environment, Research Teaching, Research Activity, the Technologies of Research Teaching

I. INTRODUCTION

TODAY the future is determined by great scientific changes, mobility of use of knowledge and velocity of new technologies. In connection with it education and science is turning to the most important field of human activity, tightly connected with other fields of public life. Within the realization of the Strategy of development of science in the Republic of Kazakhstan a great attention is paid for the problems of quality assurance of scientific-research work and raising a patent activity, the growth of capitalization of scientific results, particularly, to increase in the rate of invention, to development of correlation of the volume of intangible assets, put on the balance.

A more possible way of successfulness of the shown tasks is lying through the advance of the programs of science intensive industry and improvement of the system of higher education and higher occupational education after institute of higher education. In this connection, a central role here is given to MA course as a system of preparation of scientific-pedagogical staff of higher qualification. The feature of the organization of studying in the MA course is determined by that a listener of the MA course can be trained to research work by giving the learner educational tasks only or including him/her into "action". It is a product of education, but doesn't come out from it directly, but is above all a consequence of self-development of a listener of the MA course, at the same time is not so "technological", such a "personal growth", the whole self-organization and a synthesis of its active and personal experience.

A.Bulatbayeva, A.Kusainov, employees of Public association "Academy of pedagogical sciences of Kazakhstan". Carry out basic and applied researches in the field of educational policy, comparative pedagogics, design of the maintenance of the higher education, an assessment of quality of education. phone/fax: + 7 (727) 2675954, e-mail address: a.bulatbaeva@yandex/kz, apnkaz@mail.ru, organization site: www.apnk.kz

At the present time in higher education of the Republic of Kazakhstan has been realized the main principles of Bolon declaration. On 12 and 12th March 2010 in the II Bolon Forum of Ministers for education of participant-countries of the Bolon process (in Budapest city, Hungary and Venue city,

Austria) Kazakhstan joined to the Bolon declaraiton and became 47th member country of the Bolon process. Into all institutes of higher education has been introduced a credit technology of education. Higher education of the country is carrying out actively joined education programs with foreign universities. Has been carried out completely transmission to three-stepped model of preparation of specialists: bachelor – master - Ph.D.

Within the transmission to the three-stepped model of higher education by the government of the Republic and the Ministry for education and science has been paid attention to MA course. In MA course of the republic, preparation is carried out in two directions: profile profound preparation, science-pedagogical preparation.

Now a contingent of learner in MA course is more 10,0 persons, from which on the basis of state order - 5,9 thousand persons. Average cost for the years 2010-2011 education year under the state order for one master was 396,0 thousand tenge. Licenses for preparation of masters staffs have got 118 institutes of higher education, including 9 national, 31 state, 9 incorporated, 5 non-civil, 64 private. State order for masters preparation has been placed in 56 institutes of higher education and 2 scientific-research institutes [1].

Realization of master programs is governed by the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan, "Education Law" of the Republic of Kazakhstan (as of 2007), a State program of development of education of the Republic of Kazakhstan for the years 2011-2020, State compulsory standard of education, Standard regulations of organization of educational process, current and total control of the Ministry for education and science of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Educational programs of MA course is realized on two directions: scientific and pedagogical, profile. Educational program of the MA course contains theoretical education covering study of cycles of base and profiling disciplines; occupational practice (pedagogical, industrial, research); scientific-research work, including fulfillment of master dissertation for scientific and pedagogical MA courses; experimental-research work, covering fulfillment of master dissertation for profile MA course; interim and total attestation. The educational component of MA course programs consists of two cycles of disciplines: base and profile, each of which if formed from compulsory component (CC) and a component on choice (CCH).

Academic freedom of MA course programs is more widely represented. So, CC makes up on scientific and pedagogical direction 32 per cent, and on profile direction 29-31 per cent. A list of the disciplines of the component is determined by an institution of high education independently. At the same time is taken into account of expectation of employers and a need of labor market [2].

In the Scientific pedagogical MA course in the list of disciplines of base compulsory component there are a History and philosophy of science, English, Psychology, and Pedagogy. A content of curriculum in the base compulsory component of the MA course on the profile direction includes the following disciplines: English, Management, and Psychology.

At a credit technology of education a volume of independent work increases, done by masters, which is divided into two types – independent work of a master under guidance of a teacher (SRMP) and that part, which is done by masters fully independently (SRM).

The important part of preparation of masters is a scientific-research work. It is given a time equal to a quantity of educational hours.

In whole the development of after institute of higher education in the Republic is conditioned by the following tendencies. First, replacement of labor with knowledge, i.e. knowledge is as a source of cost. Is actualized a need for accumulating of intellectual capital, accumulation and distribution of information and experience, creation of backgrounds for spread and placement of knowledge [3].

Secondly, the tendencies of advancing progress of live knowledge. Knowledge and creative potential of a worker becomes a main factor of effectiveness of economical system. At the same time the main portion of human activity is expressed not in the process of influence on material things of labor, but on the process “games between people” [4].

Third, development of anthropocentric understanding of organization of labor, when happens a spread of functions of an employee and arises a need for development of universal skills.

Fourthly, reinforcing a network development of education and reinforcing communicative flows. In connection with this, personality becomes an organizer of educational space, a realizator of individual trajectory of education.

Fifth, social labor, i.e., actualization of the need for development of ability to re-building a reality, nomination of needs for self-expression in the foreground, aspiration for self-expression. In those conditions there are needs for specialists with high intellectual potential and able to generate new knowledge.

Six, thinking an essence of development of innovation industry, actualization of use of intellectual recourses, progress of science and technologies, stimulating of innovational activity.

In this connection the state policy of quality of after institute of higher education in the foreground offers intellect intensive, science intensive, education intensive, managerial market economical systems of state scale.

In this context it is need to develop the following competences of a researcher, as requirements for a level of skills of the graduates of MA course, which are ready for researching pedagogical phenomena and processes, use of different procedures and methods. This:

- ability to indentify, find out and obtain necessary knowledge;
- skills to plan and analyze a theoretical and experimental research, ability of critically estimate data and make conclusions;
- able to estimate opportunities of use of new and modern technologies in the field of their specialty.

As we see, the MA course is a level of education, which is directed on working out at a graduate of universal approach to concrete occupational activity. As comparison with other kinds of higher education more hours and efforts are given to disciplines of specialization, research designs and industrial practice. Besides it, MA course apart form of comprehensive specialization is aimed at development of systemic, analytic and integrated competences (Figure 1). Graduates not only are able to use finished knowledge, but work out new, translate them to other individuals.

Fig. 1 Content of scientific-research preparation of a master

The research direction of master preparation leaves it's sign on the content of education, forms of organization of educational process, scientific activity of masters. Comprehensive preparation of students-masters for scientific-research and scientific-pedagogical activity includes:

- mastering methods, ways and procedures of fulfillment of scientific work and academic lessons;
- acquisition of skills of organization of scientific and pedagogical work;
- study and mastering methods and procedures of work with a massive of scientific information;
- having computer and other technical means, used in scientific-research activity;

- accumulation of experience of planning and organizing scientific-research work when taking scientific-research practice;
- accumulation of experience of planning and conduction of academic work when taking scientific-research practice;
- a great attention during preparation of masters is paid to mastering a method of scientific researches, preparation of scientific reports, articles, essays, master dissertation. In acquisition by master of skills of scientific research an important role play annual scientific conferences, devoted to topical problems of education. A great importance is given to improving to scientific leaders of master preparation.

III. A NECESSITY FOR ORGANIZATION OF RESEARCH TRAINING

A great attention paid to the research work in the system of MA course preparation, in great level is conditioned by its specifics, its orientation on development of cognitive activity, on independent acquisition of knowledge. Scientific – research activity as a part of research work will allow solving the following tasks: develops scientific thinking, translate a subject content, forms research competences and brings personality. A content of the research work is the studying of universal ways of acquisition knowledge and development of universal skills - logical, informational, communicative and organizational.

According to the date of foreign researchers the efficiency of research training is possible if:

- we admit that the very studied bring a value experience for studying;
- students are able to take responsibilities for their own education;
- students have some freedom of choice and they are active;
- are used various methods of estimation and are stimulated the methods of self-assessment;
- moderation of work load;
- physical and social context of study of adequate for active approaches of education;
- students feel that effort leads to success and to acquaintance of this success;
- students can develop their own repertory of skills from that they practice with education[5].

Such a model of the research education will allow a learner to gain skills of joined work, work out tolerance, develops attention and systemize knowledge in subject field, allows to work out individual strategy of education and other many things.

Efficiency of research education in a great level is connected with projection of personal-orientated educational space. In such an educational space not only are expressed knowledge, but are revealed, formed and realized personal of learner masters. In a such environment prevails an emotional positive mood to work, occupation is attractive and effective. A teacher doesn't simply create a creative atmosphere, but continuously turns to a subjective experience of masters, i.e. to the experience of own life activity.

And, before all, the very important is that he/she acknowledges originality and uniqueness of each learner.

I.S. Yakimanskaya confirms that on the ground of personal-orientated education lies recognition of individuality, originality, self-assessment of each man, his development not as "collective subject", but above all as an individual, enriched with his individual subjective experience [6].

The personal-orientated system of education pays its attention on individual development of a man, on his abilities and gifts. Besides it, one of the tasks of personal orientated education is a task of formation of personal qualities of raising man. In this case it is important to imagine what the personality is.

Above all when interpreting that notion is paid attention to the social essence of personality. By this N.M.Amasov's opinion is interesting, which in one of his philosophical work stated that in the bases of personality one should make out motivation direction, power of character, ability to self-management, a level of informing and, of course, the level of intellectual progress [7].

Meanwhile, *the features of personal-orientated educational occupation* is follows:

a) Construction of the didactic material of different types, kind and forms, determination of purpose, place and time of its use in the lessons.

b) Thinking by a teacher opportunities for independent appearance of learners. Giving them some opportunities to ask questions, to say original ideas and hypothesizes.

c) Organization of change of thoughts, opinions, estimations. Stimulating learners for addition and analysis of replies of their friends.

d) Use of the subjective experience and support on intuition of each student. Application of difficult situations, arouse during lessons, as a field of showing knowledge.

e) Aspiration for creation of situation of success for each learner.

f) Inspiration of learners to search of alternative information while preparing for seminar, practicum and etc.

g) Elaborate alternation of the types of work, types of tasks that decreases fatigability of learners.

h) Survey for learners.

In the system of the personal-orientated education a teacher and a learner are as *equal partners in rights*, bearer of various, necessary experience. Occupational position of a teacher is that in order to know and relate respectful to any opinions of the learner on the content of discussed theme.

A teacher is to think not only that which material to inform, but to guess that what of this material there is in the subjective experience of learners, as result of their previous education and own life activity. Meanwhile to discuss "versions" not in a strict situation (right - wrong), but in a dialogue in the equal right, to generalize these "versions", to mark out and support adequate lessons to the theme, tasks and education.

In such conditions learners will aspire to be heard, to say their opinions in active on the discussed theme, offer, without

being afraid, their versions. Discussing them, a teacher will form team knowledge, not a simply take from classes finished examples, prepared by them for mastering.

Choosing a didactic material, a teacher are obliged not only to take into account of its general complexity, but of each learner's individual preferences. The collection of such a material one should use flexibly during the lesson, without it he will not be personal-orientated in original sense of this world. When preparing for the lesson it is need to project beforehand all possible types of communications, subject to educational purposes, all forms of cooperation between learners.

Between personal interactions in the process of lesson are provided by:

- use of different kinds of communications;
- taking into account of personal features, requirements for between team interactions (distribution on teams, pairs and etc.);
- anticipation of possible changes in organization of team work, correction of them in the process of lesson.

Effectiveness of the lesson is determined by generalizing obtained knowledge and skills; analyzing the results of team and individual work; by especial attention to the process of fulfillment of tasks, not only to a final results; discussion at the end of lesson of that what “we learnt”, how much we liked (didn't like) and why.

One can mark out the follow methods of organization of research training when preparing masters: initiation of the activity of masters; providing the ways of productive activity, work with variety of informational texts; stimulating individual choice and motivation of creative work; providing development of criticality of thinking, change of value judgments; activization of cooperation in team work; training of models, strategies of behavior and communicative skills; assistance for self-management of independent activity, acquisition of “I - massage”, taking decisions.

On the basis of before said, we offer the following scheme of study of the theme within educational lesson or their cycle:

- problem topicality of the theme, within which is formed emotional relation to the theme and needs for studying it (cognitive motivation), investigation of a problem, leading to the needs for studying educational question;
- a result of research process;
- correction by a teacher of the process depending on a level of readiness of learners;
- problematization of individual notions, building of hierarchy of notions (tree of notions), links;
- a series of research tasks; discussion of tasks by teams of master (marking out of sings, substantial signs, functions, main sign as a source of development), search of solutions; theoretical determination of notions;
- analysis of educational material by using new notions (use of texts-sources, cards);
- creative tasks for understanding the processes of internal development of pedagogical phenomena, forecasting theme, interpretation, control – over skills to operate notions, creative types of control (it is possible specific practicum,

where happen joined various skills – theoretical knowledge, psychological, pedagogical, for example, the parts of theme and etc.).

- in the process of study continuous activity of masters on assessment of own results.

One should emphasize that in a research model of education a teacher occupies a new *occupational position* – at the same time both of teacher and psychologist, able to carry out complete survey for each learner in the process of their individual development, personal formation.

IV. CONCLUSION

The results of the research and practical academic experience show that one of the directions of improvement of educational process in the MA course is change of main approaches and principles in organizing of class studies, which must provide mastering the norms of research activity, to raise the culture of scientific thinking and “launch” the mechanisms of self-education and self-development. From the strategy of informing and education today one should pass to active and interactive methods, reflexive-active kinds of organization of educational process, promoting to build general meaningful field. Such forms of organization of team thought activity, as discussion, debates, problem-active and organizational-thinking games, public expertise of finished materials, round table and meetings with leading scientists of the republic, provide to master the ways of system thinking, techniques of thought activity, the methods of research, communicative and axiological activity. In the situation of clash and agreement of the points of view, discussions of different scientific flows there will happen both accept of occupational ideals of scientific communities and “crystallization” of own scientific style, which is realized in the individual creative research work.

Thus, content and forms of the educational process in the MA course must be a progressing environment, in which will happen formation of scientists-researchs, knowing their mission, having got research positions, able to innovational activity in different fields of social practice.

REFERENCES

- [1] *Conception of academic mobility of learners of higher education in the Republic of Kazakhstan. (as of 19.01.2011.)*, Ministry for Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Astana.
- [2] *State comprehensive standard of education of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Education after institution of higher education. Main provisions. GOSO of the RK 5.04.033 – 2011 (as of June 17, 2011, # 261)*, Ministry for Education and Science of the RK, Astana.
- [3] B. Milner, “Management of knowledge – challenges in the XXI century”, *Questions of economy*, №9, pp.109-113, 1999.
- [4] E.V. Denisikina, *Evolution of factors of production in economical systems. // Collection of reports of international scientific-practical conference “Global and regional aspects of economy”*, Barnaul, 2001, pp.155-161.
- [5] The Bridge Project: Inventory of Mobility Opportunities In and About Germany For Canadian Post-Secondary Students, Final Report, April 15, 2005
- [6] I.S. Yakimanskaya, *Personal-oriented education in the modern school*. Moscow: September, 1996, 96 p.
- [7] N.M. Amosov, *Modeling thinking and psychic*. Kiev: Naukova dumka, 1965, 125 p.